

INCREASE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS RESISTANCE
TO TRANSVERSAL TENSION, INTERLAYER SHEAR AND COMPRESSION

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The resistance of transversally isotropic fibre reinforced composite unit volume to transversal tension, interlayer shear and compression was studied. Its strength in this case was found to be dependent on matrix mechanical properties and its adhesion to fibres along the interface. With the increase of the filling degree, the contribution of interface adhesion into the composite total strength is increased. It is shown that for cohesion type of shear and transversal tension failure, interface adhesion should be 0.65-1.3 of matrix strength.

Direct correlation is established between composites compressive strength, interlayer shear strength and transversal pull strength. It is confirmed experimentally that the increase of matrix strength and rigidity due to reinforcement by discrete fibres and also the increase of fibre-matrix adhesion due to carbon fibre whiskerization and various methods of liquid and gas phase carbon fibres surface activation treatment provides considerable increase of carbon fibre reinforced plastics strength at these types of loading. The efficiency of carbon surface treatment may be judged by the ratio of mechanical and adhesive components of matrix-fibre bond strength, depending on specific surface size and its absorption activity.